

Table 1: The detail of dataset used in this study. We augmented the dataset from the prior work of Mirsaeed *et al.* Mirsaedi and Rigby 2020.

Name	Files	Review PRs	Years	Developers	Review Requests
Roslyn	12,313	8,646	5	469	1,546
Rust	12,472	17,499	9	2,720	128
Kubernetes	12,792	32,400	5	2,617	26,164

Figure 1: Percentage of change sets impacted by stale recommendations. Each set of bars shows results for cHRev (left), Sofia (middle), and WLRRec (right) in each period.

Figure 2: The top-3 most frequently stale recommendations and their share of all suggested leavers for cHRev (leftmost bar), Sofia (middle bar), and WLRRec (right bar) for various periods under different conditions

Figure 3: Share of top-N significant leavers for different review set size (K) for different projects and approaches. The increase of Share with considering more top-N project leavers increased in logarithmic trend.

Figure 4: The distribution of lingering time for the top-3 reviewers over quarterly periods.

References

- Mirsaeedi, Ehsan and Peter C Rigby (2020). “Mitigating turnover with code review recommendation: Balancing expertise, workload, and knowledge distribution”. In: *Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE 42nd International Conference on Software Engineering*, pp. 1183–1195.